

Dangerous Liaisons: Portraits of Two Indians in the Court of Napoleon

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Abstract

This paper looks at the career of Catherine Grand *née* Worle, born in the Danish colony of Tranquebar in 1761 and a resident of Chandernagore in her childhood and early youth. Catherine's marriage with an East India Company officer, George François Grand, and her affair with Philip Francis, a member of Warren Hastings's governing council, was one of the longest-running scandals of its time, leading to a libel action, a divorce and a duel. However, this paper is interested in Madame Grand's career in France after the mid-1780s where she became part of the smart set and subsequently the mistress of Charles Maurice de Talleyrand-Périgord, foreign minister under Napoleon and one of the few survivors from the *ancien régime*. Their relationship created uproar and Talleyrand was ordered by Napoleon to either marry her or leave her, so in 1802 they married in the presence of the First Consul and Madame Bonaparte. But despite being a friend of Madame Bonaparte, and one of the first ladies of the court, Madame Grand now the Princessa de Beneventowas referred to in the most disparaging terms by contemporary commentators, who seem to have gone along unquestioningly with Talleyrand's own view of Catherine as '*une indienne, bien belle, bien paresseuse, la plus desoccupée de toutes les femmes que j'ai jamais rencontrées*' i.e. an Indian, very beautiful, very idle, one of the laziest women I have ever known.' The fact that she was considered to be '*une indienne*' seems to have triggered off all sorts and conditions of xenophobia, and she was widely perceived as an outsider who could not master even the rudiments of the French language. Talleyrand wrote of her as '*Une Indienne bien belle*,' Napoleon at St Helena referred to her as '*Anglaise ou Indienne*;' and Capefigue in the *Biographie Universelle* referred to her as '*rare and nonchalante beauté Indienne*.' This paper will look at a number of such accounts, as well as at two famous paintings of Madame Grand, to report on what may well have been a textbook instance of orientalism.

Key words: Mme Grand, Chandernagore, Talleyrand-Périgord, Napoleon, indienne.

On 24 January, 2002, the auctioning house of Sotheby's of New York

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presented a special theme auction entitled, ‘Revolution in Art: 1770-1830’. Among the highlights of the sale was a ‘Portrait of Catherine Worlée, Princesse de Talleyrand-Périgord, circa 1808,’ by François-Pascal-Simon Baron Gérard, which was estimated to sell for \$1.4/1.8 million. According to the pre-sale bulletin,

[T]he sitter was the daughter of a French official stationed in India and a woman whose life mirrored the turbulent time in which she lived. She was married in India at the age of sixteen, estranged from her husband and was residing in Paris by 1783. It was there that she gained some notoriety for her numerous affairs with wealthy and married men, eventually fleeing Paris for England, and returning after the fall of Robespierre. Soon after her return she was arrested and imprisoned for espionage and rescued by Napoleon’s Minister of Foreign Affairs, Charles Maurice de Talleyrand-Périgord. They were soon living together and their relationship created an uproar. Talleyrand was ordered by Napoleon to either marry her or leave her, so in 1802 they married in the presence of the First Consul and Madame Bonaparte.¹

Now Sotheby’s brief bio is fairly typical of what history has chosen to remember of Catherine, and the space that is accorded her in accounts of pre- and post-revolution France. For instance, in Simon Schama’s glittering *Citizens: A Chronicle of the French Revolution*,² Catherine is mentioned just once, and that too in passing. On the other hand, a portrait of hers – painted by Elisabeth Vigée-Lebrun, that neglected recorder of the *ancien régime* – is accorded pride of place along with portraits of Marie Antoinette and other court favourites. In contrast, her husband Talleryand, one of the greatest political survivors of all times, straddles both ends of Schama’s monumental account. The same neglect of Catherine marks most contemporary accounts of the revolution and its aftermath. Catherine is mentioned only in passing, if at all, and usually in the most disparaging terms. Most

commentators seem to have gone along unquestioningly with Talleyrand's own view of Catherine as 'une indienne, bien belle, bien paresseuse, la plus desoccupée de toutes les femmes que j'ai jamais rencontrées'³ – i.e. 'an Indian, very beautiful, very idle, one of the laziest women I have ever known.'

But before we consider the ways in which Catherine and her Indian-ness were constructed in the French court, let us recapitulate certain key moments in her eventful life in India. Catherine Noel Werlee was born in the Danish colony of Tranquebar on the Coromandel coast on 21 November 1762; her father Pierre Werlee was French and sometime harbour-master in Pondicherry, while her mother was Laurence Allamay, possibly a Danish subject. Shortly after her birth, the family moved to Chandannagar where Pierre Werlee was appointed *Capitaine du Port* by Monsieur Chevalier, the governor of Chandannagar. Chevalier was known for throwing lavish parties at his country seat, Ghyretty House, and during the 1770s, these parties were regularly attended by governor-general Warren Hastings and his cronies. One such hanger-on was a youngish man called George François Grand, who had first come to India in 1766 but was thwarted in his attempts to make a career. His second innings in 1776 proved to be more fruitful and he managed to obtain a writership in the office of Hastings. To cut a long story short, George met Catherine at one of M. Chevalier's parties, the two fell in love and got married on 10 July 1777. Catherine was a few months short of sixteen at that time, and by all accounts, considered one of the most exquisite beauties in and around Calcutta.

The newly-weds took up residence in a garden-house near Alipore and seemed to have had a happy first year of married life. But all this was to change on December 8, 1778. Much later, in 1814, George would publish his own account of the events that were set in motion on that fateful night. In it, George wrote:

On December 8, 1778, I went out of my house, about nine

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o'clock, the happiest, as I thought myself, of men; and between eleven and twelve o'clock returned the same night to it as miserable as any being could well feel. [...] Scarcely had I sat down to supper at my benefactor, Mr Barwell's society... that I was suddenly struck by the deepest of anguish and pain. A servant, who was in the habit of attending Mrs Grand, came and whispered to me that Mr Francis was caught in my house, and secured by my jemadar.⁴

On reaching his house, George found not Philip Francis but George Shee (later Sir George Shee) tied to a chair while Mr Shore (afterwards Lord Teignmouth) stood entreating the jemadar Rambux to release him. From Rambux's account, it transpired that Francis had scaled the compound wall with the aid of a folding ladder, had broken into Catherine's bedroom and had subsequently been apprehended and tied up by the domestic staff. However, his friends, who had been lurking outside rushed in, freed Francis and created a fracas in which Francis was able to make his escape. Rambux and his party, not to be outdone, took George Shee as prisoner. This was the scene that greeted George Grand when he rushed back to his garden-house in Alipore.

The Mr Francis mentioned above was none other than Philip Francis, one of the members of the Bengal Council and sworn enemy of Warren Hastings, with whom he was later to fight a famous duel over the conduct of the Maratha campaign. A study of Francis's journal during this period does reveal the degree of his interest in Catherine. On November 23, i.e. just two weeks before the incident, there had been a ball in Francis's house at which the Grands were also invited. The journal entry for November 24, the very next day, is suggestive; 'Amor vincit omnia; job for Wood, the salt agent.'⁵ One may point out here that at the time, George Grand was secretary to the salt committee. These, and other journal entries, suggest that Francis's attentions towards Catherine was neither entirely

unwelcome, nor unreciprocated. However, the journal entry for December 8, the night of the break-in, was a terse ‘At night the diable a quatre at the house of G.F. Grand, Esq.’

A very full account of this incident, as well as the subsequent lawsuit, can be found in H.E. Busteed’s celebrated book, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*. George Grand sued Francis in the Supreme Court, and a bench consisting of Elijah Impey, Rober Chambers and Justice Hyde heard the case in February 1779. What emerged was an extraordinary account of midnight alarms, folding ladders, fisticuffs, close shaves and on the whole, thoroughly ruffianly behaviour by four high-ranking company officials. After a month-long hearing, the judges found the plaintiff’s petition justified and Francis was fined to the tune of fifty thousand sicca rupees.

In the meantime, however, Catherine had been effectively given marching orders by George. After the break-in by Francis, George summoned his in-laws from Chandanagar and asked them to take Catherine away. Before she left, Catherine sought an interview with her husband. In the words of George :

[I]t lasted three hours, interrupted with the most poignant lamentations. From her own lips I learnt an unvarnished relation of the base arts employed for the seduction of a stranger and (sic) attained only to her sixteenth year. I pitied her from my heart. I sincerely forgave her and with a sorrow approaching to distraction we parted.⁶

Now that Catherine was back in Chandannagar, there was little to stop Francis from renewing his advances. It is not very clear how willingly Catherine suffered his attentions but it seems fairly certain that by July 1779, Francis had installed Catherine in a rented house in Hooghly. Quoting from Francis’s journal, Busteed shows how Francis made frequent trips up the river during the second half of 1779. This was followed by Francis installing Catherine under his own roof. As Duff Cooper, one of the many biographers of Talleryand, reports:

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Sir Philip, however, persuaded her to come back to him and for a year lodged her under the same roof with Lady Francis – whom he persuaded that their relations were purely platonic – a feat in comparison with which the authorship of the letters of Junius sinks into insignificance.⁷

I should add here that before his arrival in India, Francis had in all probability written a series of letters titled ‘Letters from Junius’ which had appeared in the *Public Advertiser* between 1769 and 1772. These letters had bitterly attacked, among others, the Duke of Grafton, Lord Mansfield and George III himself.

However, the following year was not a happy one for Francis. As is well known, he fell out seriously with Warren Hastings over the conduct of the Maratha campaign. A duel between the two took place on August 17, 1780 at the Belvedere grounds and Francis was badly injured, though not fatally. It is, therefore, not surprising that as soon as he was sufficiently recovered, Francis left India in a tearing hurry, in December that year. What is intriguing, however, is Catherine’s departure in another ship exactly one week later, possibly in the company of one Thomas Lewin, lately employed as a writer with the military department at Fort St George, the seat of government in Madras. Again, it is difficult to be absolutely certain, but it does seem likely that Francis had tired of Catherine by then and had few scruples in leaving her to fend for herself.

From this point onwards, till her meeting with Talleyrand in 1799, little is known about Catherine’s life. It is significant that the trail becomes cold precisely at the moment when Catherine begins to take control of her own life. First in Chandanangar, and then in Calcutta, Catherine had been completely at the mercy of circumstances. She must have realised that as long as she remained in India, her immediate past would militate against any attempts on her part to lead a normal life. After leaving Calcutta in the company

of Thomas Lewin, it appears the couple spent some time travelling randomly in Europe. In the words of Busted:

[H]e had so ingratiated himself with his fair companion, and had so beguiled her of her loneliness, that she accompanied him from Cadiz to Lisbon, and thence in a Portuguese vessel to England, where she yielded to his solicitations and threw in her lot with him temporarily. They stayed some time in London, at a house in Russell Place, Fitzroy Square, and went thence to Paris, where they separated.⁸

Then Busted adds, in avuncular vein:

Before we feel inclined to morally exalt ourselves and give thanks that we are not as other men are, or were, let us bear in mind that at this period, the gentleman, good looking, amiable, and winning, was about twenty-eight, and that the lady, one of the most physically attractive women of her time, was only eighteen. Also how tempting any distraction, let alone love-making, must have been to a young couple to mitigate ennui amidst the appalling dullness of a tedious voyage – and that in a Dutch ship.⁹

The paucity of material on Catherine from 1783 to 1799 prevents us from forming any definite picture of her life during this period. She lived in Paris and appeared to have hung around with the smart set which included Marie Antoinette, the Comte d'Artois and Josephine de Beauharnais, later to become empress. According to Duff Cooper, Catherine had been the mistress of Lessart, the Minister for Foreign Affairs before the French Revolution. But Lessart was killed during the gruesome September massacres of 1791 and Catherine prudently fled to England in August 1792. According to de Villemarest, another of Talleyrand's biographers, just before her escape Catherine had seen from her window the massacre of the porter of her house on Rue de Mirabeau (later Rue de Montblanc). She left hurriedly with her maid and arrived in Dover with only twelve *louis*

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in her purse.¹⁰

We now move forwards another five years in time, to 1797. By then, Napoleon's star was firmly on the ascendant and the ideals of the revolution were gradually being jettisoned. Talleyrand was back in France and in the thick of politics after a long exile in England and the United States. Having managed to escape the Terror, Talleyrand had had plenty of time to hone his political and entrepreneurial skills in New England. As Simon Schama reports:

[H]e even dreamed up the original idea of selling American lands in India to the great moneyed plunderers of the British East India Company, who would acquire attractive investments while bypassing all the scrutiny (and taxes) they incurred when remitting payments to London.¹¹

But I digress. Thanks to the intervention of his friend Germaine de Stael, Talleyrand was able to set sail from Manhattan in June 1796. Exactly one year later, he was the Republic's Minister for Foreign Affairs,' replacing the previous incumbent Charles Delacroix. Talleyrand also replaced him in the bed of Madame Delacroix and the resultant progeny was Eugene Delacroix, 'the greatest Romantic of the new age sired by the most formidable skeptic of the old,'¹² to quote Schama again.

The accounts of the first meeting between Talleyrand and Catherine are conflicting. One school of thought holds that Catherine and Talleyrand met in London, returned to Paris under a fictitious name and continued to live incognito with Talleyrand till 1797. According to Duff Cooper, during this time she was arrested on a charge of espionage and Talleyrand had to write to Barras, the director, for her release. It is in this letter that Talleyrand described Catherine as 'very beautiful, very idle, one of the laziest women I have ever known,' an appraisal which soon gained widespread

currency. To this was added a reputation for naiveté and stupidity – indeed, at this time it became the fashion to attribute almost every absurd remark that was made in Paris to Catherine. According to another account, and here I quote Busted:

Madame Grand naively presented herself to the Minister of External Relations, in alarm at the report she had heard from the best authority, that Bonaparte was about to invade England, and had promised to give the Bank of England up to pillage; her visit was with the object of begging Talleyrand to get a guarantee that her property, which was all locked up there, should be saved for her. [...]The story goes that the Foreign Minister saw the joke that had been played upon her, but being too polite to tell her so, quieted her with a document guaranteeing the safe delivery of her plate, jewels, etc. to any person she may name, as soon as ever Bonaparte's army had entered London.¹³

But the person most enraged at the liaison between Talleyrand and Catherine was none other than First Consul, Napoleon himself. There was little love lost between the two anyway and Talleyrand's infatuation with Catherine irritated Napoleon beyond all bounds of reason. He was obsessed with the setting up a court which was morally irreproachable – on one occasion it was brought to his notice that an English newspaper had printed a critical report on Talleyrand's womanizing. Flying into a rage, he sent for Talleyrand and told him:

No wonder that we are vilified in England when we expose ourselves to it by the conduct of our public ministers; the envoys and ambassadors for Foreign Courts are, I understand, compelled to wait upon your mistress: this must not continue.¹⁴

To which, Talleyrand is said to have retorted: 'Neither shall it. They shall henceforth wait upon my wife.'¹⁵ This is the first indication we have of a possible marriage between the two lovers. But this was

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dismissed out of hand by Napoleon – also, Talleyrand, who had been a bishop before the Revolution, was then serving a ban of excommunication pronounced on him by Pope Pius VI in 1790. He had been secularized in 1801 but Napoleon considered it indecorous for him to marry so quickly after his secularization. In any case, Talleyrand interpreted his secularization as an annulment of priestly celibacy and authorization to enter the matrimonial state.

The war between the two men over Catherine hereafter took strange twists and turns. Finding Talleyrand in a rebellious mood, Napoleon tried a new tack. Talleyrand's residence at Rue de Bac also functioned as the Foreign Office and news came to Napoleon that some of the ambassadors there were unhappy at the idea of being received by the lady presiding there. The First Consul sent for Talleyrand again and told him that Catherine must leave. Catherine, however, anticipating precisely such a move from the First Consul, went to her old friend Josephine and entreated her to arrange an interview with Napoleon. This interview duly took place and I must again quote Busted for what transpired:

At the interview with the First Consul she fell on her knees – and very probably it was the old story – women's best weapons, tears and cajoling, triumphed once again, for the softened Bonaparte (who was wont to say that “there were two things becoming to women – rouge and tears”) dismissed her saying, “I see only one way of managing this – let Talleyrand marry you, and all will be arranged. You must bear his name or you cannot appear in this house.”¹⁶

For Napoleon, to think was to act. He gave Talleyrand exactly 24 hours to think about his ultimatum. The master diplomat had been painted into a corner, thanks to Catherine's initiative and Josephine's special pleading on her behalf. Talleyrand did not forgive Josephine for this and had some measure of revenge a few years later by supporting Napoleon's scheme for a divorce. The marriage between Charles-Maurice de Talleyrand-Périgord and

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Catherine Noel Werlee took place on September 10, 1802 before the Mayor of the 10th arrondissement of Paris.

There is no reason to believe that Talleyrand was overjoyed at this sudden turn of events. His enemies gloated over his discomfiture at having to marry a woman he had never ever been in love with. Talleyrand's mother was so enraged at the marriage that she henceforth refused to accept the allowance her son had settled on her. As for Napoleon, there was little change in his contemptuous attitude towards Catherine. As Madame de Remusat testifies:

He treated her coldly, even rudely; never admitted her to the distinctions of the rank to which she was raised without making a difficulty about it; and did not disguise the repugnance with which she inspired him, even while Talleyrand possessed his confidence. Talleyrand bore all this, never allowed the slightest complaint to escape him, and arranged so that his wife should appear but seldom at Court. She received all distinguished foreigners on certain days, and on certain other days the Government officials; she made no visits, none were expected from her. Provided each person bowed to her on entering and leaving his salon, Talleyrand asked no more.¹⁷

One feels that Madame de Remusat credits Talleyrand with too much solicitousness for his wife. After all, it was Talleyrand who wrote in his journal towards the end of his life:

My passion for Madame de Talleyrand was soon extinguished, because she was merely possessed by beauty. The influence of personal charms is limited, curiosity forms the greatest ingredient of this kind of love.¹⁸

Even more telling is Talleyrand's laconic response to the news of the death of Catherine in 1835 (by then, the two had been separated for almost two decades): 'Ce ma position a beaucoup simplifiée' (This

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greatly simplifies my position).

At this point, let us step back from this chronological recital and consider why Catherine found it so difficult to be accepted by the *beau monde* of Paris, and why commentators and historians have repeatedly drawn a discreet veil over that part of Talleyrand's life which concerned Catherine. The fact that Catherine was considered to be *une indienne* seems to have triggered off all sorts and conditions of xenophobia. She was widely perceived as an outsider who could not master even the rudiments of the French language. In fact, one of the many malapropisms she was credited with will illustrate this point: on being asked where she was from, Catherine, instead of saying 'Je suis des Indes' (which means I am from India), reportedly said Je suis dinde (which means I am a turkey). Instances like this can be multiplied but I will mention just one, which was related by Napoleon to his physician O'Meara in St Helena:

The triumph of Talleyrand is the triumph of immorality. A priest united to another man's wife, and who has paid her husband a large sum of money to leave her with him; a man who has sold everything, betrayed everybody and every side. I forbade Madame Talleyrand the court, first, because she was a disreputable character, and because I found out that some Genoese merchants had paid her four hundred thousand francs, in order to gain some commercial favours by means of her husband [...].¹⁹

How true these stories are there is no way to ascertain but one or two other stories cast some degree of doubt on Catherine's legendary stupidity. When Catherine first appeared in court after her marriage, Napoleon, in his usual hectoring way, expressed his hope to her that the good conduct of *citoyenne* Talleyrand would cause the indiscretions of Madame Grand to be forgotten; whereupon she rejoined that she could do no better than follow the example of *citoyenne* Bonaparte. Again, the poet Thomas Moore recounts that the princess sat next to him at dinner in 1821 and that he found her a

great admirer of his poem *Lalla Rookh*.

On the other hand, there seemed to be no dearth of accounts (usually male) extolling Catherine's beauty. Take, for instance, this account by Colmache, Talleyrand's secretary:

Madame Grand had the kind of beauty which is the rarest and most admired in Europe. She was tall and slight, with that languor in her carriage peculiar to creole ladies; her eyes were well open and affectionate, her features delicate, her golden hair playing in numberless curls, set off a forehead as white as a lily. She had, moreover, preserved a child-like grace in her expression and throughout her whole person; it was this which distinguished her from those Parisian ladies who might, perhaps, rival her in beauty, and made her resemble rather Madame Recamier than Mme. Tallien or Mme. de Beauharnais.²⁰

Or take the testimony of Philip Francis:

Mrs Grand was the most beautiful woman in Calcutta. She was tall, elegantly formed, the stature of a nymph, a complexion of unrivalled beauty, and auburn hair of the most luxuriant profusion; fine blue eyes, with black eye-lashes and eye-brows that gave her eye-brows the most piquant singularity.²¹

Another contemporary, Madame de Remusat had this to offer:

I have heard it said that she was one of the most charming women of her time. She was tall, and her figure had all the suppleness of and grace so common to women born in the East. Her complexion was dazzling, her eyes the brightest blue, and her slightly turned up nose gave her, singularly enough, a look of Talleyrand himself.²²

And according to an unnamed French enthusiast, she was 'la plus belle chevelure blonde qui ait peut-etre jamais existé.'²³

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From the above, it is clear that most of the accounts about Catherine's appearance are textbook instances of orientalism – references to her race, her so-called eastern origins and the exotic nature of her beauty occur with unfailing regularity. Also intriguing is the insistence on her Indian-ness. Busteded draws attention to this when he writes: 'It is customary, especially among French writers, to speak of Mrs Grand as an "Indian."' Talleyrand himself writes of her as 'Une Indienne bien belle,' and Napoleon at St Helena referred to her as 'Anglaise ou Indienne;' Capefique in the *Biographie Universelle* speaks of her as 'rare et nonchalante beauté Indienne.'²⁴ Obviously the term Indian here has been used imprecisely, and in the case of Napoleon, even interchangeably with English. It is my tentative suggestion that this ignorance coincided with the death of the French colonial dream in India. The last throw of the dice had probably been Napoleon's Egyptian campaign, but with the defeat in the Battle of Aboukir Bay, it must have been clear even to him that the fight for India had been lost.

Endnotes :

¹ 'Revolution in Art 1770-1830'; <https://sothebys.gcs-web.com/static-files/9dc0b2ae-bc08-414a-b5c3-b0f2785b7ca5>. Accessed 06.07.19.

² Simon Schama, *Citizens: A Chronicle of the French Revolution*; Reprint edition (New York: Vintage Books, 1990). All quotes are from the 2004 Googlebooks edition.

Accessed 06.07.19.

³ Quoted in *Revue des Cours Littéraires*, 5.26 (30 May 1868), p. 26.

⁴ H. E. Busteded, *Echoes of Old Calcutta: Being Chiefly Reminiscences of the Days of Warren Hastings* (London: Thacker, Spinks, 1908; first pbd. 1882), p. 234.

⁵ Joseph Parkes and Herman Merivale, *Memoirs of Sir Philip Francis, K.C.B.: with Correspondence and Journals*, vol. II (London: Longmans, Green, 1867), p. 137.

⁶ 'Madame Grand,' *Macmillan's Magazine*, vol. 82 (1900), p. 384.

⁷ Alfred Duff Cooper, *Talleyrand* (Pickle Partners Publishing, rpt., 2015);

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first published 1932); www.picklepartnerspublishing.com.

⁸ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 275.

⁹ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 275.

¹⁰ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 285.

¹¹ Schama, *Citizens* (2004).

¹² Schama, *Citizens* (2004).

¹³ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 287.

¹⁴ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 291.

¹⁵ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 291.

¹⁶ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 292.

¹⁷ Madame de Remusat, *Memoirs of the Empress Josephine* (1910), quoted in Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 293.

¹⁸ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 309 n.

¹⁹ Charles Villemarest, *Life of Prince Talleyrand*, vol. III (London: Edward Churton, 1836), p. 174.

²⁰ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 290.

²¹ Parkes and Merivale, *Memoirs of Sir Philip Francis*, p. 145.

²² Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 290.

²³ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 231.

²⁴ Busteed, *Echoes from Old Calcutta*, p. 231.

²⁵ ‘Madame Grand (Catherine Noele Worlée, 1762–1835), Later Madame Talleyrand-Périgord, Princesse de Bénévent, 1783’, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/110002351>. Accessed 07.07.19.

²⁶ Schama, *Citizens* (2004).